

Flux Requirement with the Constraint of Hardness and Heat-affected Zone Area in Submerged Arc Welding

Dr. Brijpal Singh

MSIT Janakpuri, New Delhi, 110058 India
brijpal.singh@msit.in

Dr. Narender Singh

MSIT Janakpuri, New Delhi 110058 India
narender_singh@msit.in

Abstract— The fuzzy logic optimization technique has been used for selection of optimal flux for making low carbon steel welds of high quality. The response surface methodology has been opted and binary, ternary phase diagrams of steels has been used for design of fluxes. The heat affected area affects the properties of base metal so it becomes of utmost importance to select it as a response. It is very important in SAW. The important weld mechanical properties are ultimate tensile strength, hardness and impact strength. The flux composition is very important in deciding the weld metal properties so efforts should be made for design, manufacturing and selection of optimal flux for the required joint properties. In this case hardness and HAZ area has been considered as main parameters as output. The optimal flux contains CaF_2 5%, FeMn 8% and NiO 5% The results obtained in this experimental study have been verified by doing confirmatory tests.

Keywords— **Optimization; Submerged arc welding; Fluxes; Hardness HAZ**

I. INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVE

The submerged arc welding was first invented in USA and it is a very old joining process. This welding is usually fully automatic and semiautomatic. The weld made with these welding consumables attain a high welding speed and high quality joints can be made. In this welding, the electrode is consumable and it is fed through a nozzle [1]. It uses a very high current and the arc is made between the electrode and work piece. A very large amount of heat is generated in SAW and it melts the electrode, workspace and flux layer which is in contact. The heat of the arc produced melts the flux and it forms a layer to protect the weld pool. The unmelted flux also works as a protection from the atmosphere. The current used in SAW is higher in comparison to SMAW. The larger heat produced gives high weld deposition rate and thick plates can be welded easily. The quality of the joint may also be very high [2, 3]. The major applications of SAW are ship building, pressure vessels manufacturing, thick pipes, gas pipe lines and structural parts.. The submerged arc welding process is widely used for making heavy steel products [4].

The electrodes in SAW are in the form of bare electrode and no coating is required. The usual coating on the electrode is done of copper to increase the conductivity of the electrode. This welding is widely used because of availability of various combination of wires and fluxes in market.

Fluxes used in SAW affects the arc properties and strength of the welded joint. [5]. Study to correlate the basicity index of the flux and parameters of welding such as current, voltage, travel speed was performed by Pandey et.al 2010 [6]. They found that flux basicity index affects composition of weld metal.. The elements transfer is very important in this welding as it decides the properties of the welds. The transfer of elements to the weld may depend upon the composition of flux and slag. The transfer of elements can be either from slag to weld metal or from flux. The elements transfer depends upon the flux composition and other

welding consumables [7-10]. In Submerged arc welding as the temperature is very high so the equilibrium conditions may not be able to predict the composition of weld metal based on chemistry. So the weld metal transfer cannot be predicted by only assuming equilibrium equations. Very little research work has been reported regarding the metal transfer in SAW and this work is very much tedious and very time consuming. More research work can be done in this regard using scientific methodology and by proper design and manufacturing of fluxes. More experimental work may be required in this field so that large data may be generated. This data base can be used for predicting the weld metal properties and elements transfer in SAW. The major challenge in structural applications for an engineer is to increase the impact strength, hardness while maintaining the heat affected area as low as possible. So in this research work an attempt has been made to optimize the flux for these two parameters. RSM design has been used so that scientific study can be done to develop the fluxes and its impact on mechanical properties of the welds.

The objectives of the study was to select an optimal flux for good hardness and low HAZ area in the weld.

II. MATERIAL SELECTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

The low carbon steel or mild steel was selected for experimental work as it has variety of applications. The fuzzy logic optimization method has been used as optimization technique. Earlier the fluxes in SAW were usually made by hit and trial runs. However this process was not scientific and was more time consuming and costly. It is also very difficult to develop the new materials by this conventional method of developing the fluxes [5, 6]. Design of experiments has been used as it is more scientific method for exploring various combinations of fluxes. As it is very difficult to explore all the possible combinations by hit and trial method and to select a optimal flux.

Kumar et al. 2015 [11] in their experimental work found the optimal levels of NiO, MnO and MgO. They suggested the model based on fuzzy logic and found a single multi response performance index for impact strength and hardness based for SiO₂ fluxes. Roy et al (2013 [12] in their work suggested grey based genetic algorithm for strength and hardness of the welds. The feed rate, stick out and travel speed were considered as parameters. The desirability approach was used by Jindal et al. 2013 [13] for optimization of UTS, Impact strength and hardness for HSLA steel. Adeyeye and Oyawale 2009 [14] studied the data obtained by Kanjilal in his experiments. They developed the mathematical programming optimization technique integrated with the xverted design used by Kanjilal. .

Datta et al. 2008 [15] used the GRA approach in combination with the Taguchi method to obtain the slag – fresh flux mixture ratio without compromising the features of weld bead geometry and HAZ width.

A. Experimental Procedure

The experimental procedure is as follows

- 1 Central composite design was adopted for designing and making of fluxes. Table no 1 depicts the designed matrix.
- 2 Flux constituents were mixed in the right proportion.
- 3 Agglomeration method was used for making the fluxes. The base components have been given in Table no 2
- 4 For doing the study beads on plates were made on thick mild steel plates of the given composition. The welding parameters were made constant and are given in Table no3.
- 5: Beads on plate were made one over the other to reduce the dilution.
- 6: The measured responses are given in Table 4 the machine used has been shown in figure 1. L, M, H represents low, medium and high values of input factors.

Table 1. Design matrix

No. of Experiment	CaF ₂ wt % A	FeMn wt% B	NiO wt % C
1	H	L	L
2	M	H	M
3	H	L	H
4	L	L	L
5	M	M	M
6	M	M	M
7	H	H	H
8	M	M	M
9	M	L	M
10	H	M	M
11	M	M	H
12	L	L	H
13	M	M	M
14	M	M	M
15	H	H	L
16	L	M	M
17	M	M	0
18	M	M	M
19	L	H	H
20	-1	+1	-1

Table2. Base constituents and additives of the flux

Flux	CaF ₂ Gm	FeMn gm	NiO gm	CaO gm	SiO ₂ gm	Al ₂ O ₃ gm
1	120	30	30	486	695	139
2	75	120	75	453	647	130
3	120	30	120	453	647	130
4	30	30	30	519	742	148
5	75	75	75	470	671	134
6	75	75	75	470	671	134
7	120	120	120	420	600	120
8	75	75	75	470	671	134
9	75	30	75	486	695	139
10	120	75	75	453	647	130
11	75	75	120	453	647	130
12	30	30	120	486	695	139
13	75	75	75	470	671	134
14	75	75	75	470	671	134
15	120	120	30	453	647	130
16	30	75	75	486	695	139
17	75	75	75	470	671	134
18	75	75	30	486	695	139
19	30	120	120	453	647	130
20	30	120	30	486	695	139

S. No.	Voltage (V)	Current (A)	Travel speed Cm/min.
1	30	475	20

Flux No.	Hardness	Heat affected Area(mm ²)
1	64	170.21
2	68	202.58
3	67	274.64
4	66	162.35
5	64	98.0
6	66	100.0
7	66	213.0
8	64	37.8
9	66	174.91
10	65	167.86
11	64	97.48
12	65	148.99
13	65	105.0
14	64	157.5
15	65	206.12
16	63	118.62
17	64	95.0
18	63	121.79
19	65	212.6
20	66	330.0

B. Fuzzy Methodology with GRA

In fuzzy logic optimization the chances of error are reduced while in GRA as we consider the two factors higher the better or lower the better. In this analysis the chances of error are there so fuzzy logic optimization method was used and grey relational analysis was considered in combination. Fuzzy methodology can be applied for multi objective optimization of parameter. In a fuzzy logic system a membership function based on certain rules is applied to an engine. The membership functions based on fuzzy logic and rules generates a fuzzy value and that value is converted in to multi Characterization performance index (MCPI) by a defuzzifier. This structure of the two-input-one-output fuzzy logic unit is depicted in Fig. 2. The input are hardness and HAZ area and output is (MCPI).

Fig.1. Fuzzy inference system

III. RESULT

The used fuzzy model consists of two inputs and one output which fuzzifies the input data using three triangular membership functions. These triangular membership have been used for the two inputs and one output. This has been depicted in figures 3(a), 3(b), 3(c) and 3(d) respectively. Using fuzzy logic rules in the Mumdani inference, multi characteristic performance index for each experiment value has been calculated using centroid method of defuzzification as shown in Table 5 (a) and (b for heat affected area and hardness). The observed results of output characteristics found in the form of MCPI shows that the value of this characteristic is maximum for experiment no2. So we can infer from this that the input parameters for flux no2 can give the optimized results. The results were also verified by doing the experiments and the results were found in the reasonable range. So the experiment no 2 can be suggested for high impact strength and low width HAZ. The fuzzy base rules are given as follows.

Fig. 3(a) Rule base for fuzzy system

Fig. 3(b) Membership function for Heat Affected Area

Fig. 3(c) Membership function for Output

Fig. 3(d) Rule viewer GFRG

Table 5(a). Rank

Heat Affected Area (HAA)				
Heat Affected Area (HAA)	Normalized value HAA	Deviation	GRC (Grey relation coefficient)	Rank
170.21	0.5469	0.453	0.5246	17
202.58	0.4361	0.564	0.4700	1
274.64	0.1895	0.811	0.3815	6
162.35	0.5738	0.426	0.5398	9
98	0.7940	0.206	0.7082	8
100	0.7871	0.213	0.7014	3
213	0.4004	0.600	0.4547	12
37.8	1.0000	0.000	1.0000	2
174.91	0.5308	0.469	0.5159	10
167.86	0.5549	0.445	0.5290	13
97.48	0.7958	0.204	0.7100	5
148.99	0.6195	0.381	0.5678	11
105	0.7700	0.230	0.6850	7
157.5	0.5903	0.410	0.5497	16
206.12	0.4240	0.576	0.4647	14
118.62	0.7234	0.277	0.6438	18
95	0.8042	0.196	0.7186	4
121.79	0.7126	0.287	0.6350	19
212.6	0.4018	0.598	0.4553	15
330	0.0000	1.000	0.3333	20

Table 5(b). Rank

Hardness				
Hardness	Normalized value Hn	Deviation	GRC (Grey relation coefficient)	Rank
64	0.2	0.8	0.3846	17
68	1	0	1.0000	1
67	0.8	0.2	0.7143	6
66	0.6	0.4	0.5556	9
64	0.2	0.8	0.3846	8
66	0.6	0.4	0.5556	3
66	0.6	0.4	0.5556	12

64	0.2	0.8	0.3846	2
66	0.6	0.4	0.5556	10
65	0.4	0.6	0.4545	13
64	0.2	0.8	0.3846	5
65	0.4	0.6	0.4545	11
65	0.4	0.6	0.4545	7
64	0.2	0.8	0.3846	16
65	0.4	0.6	0.4545	14
63	0	1	0.3333	18
64	0.2	0.8	0.3846	4
63	0	1	0.3333	19
65	0.4	0.6	0.4545	15
66	0.6	0.4	0.5556	20

V Conclusions

- 1 Response surface methodology has been adopted for design of welding fluxes and the manufacturing of fluxes was done by agglomeration method.
- 2 As we have to optimize the two output parameters and we desire high hardness and low width of HAZ area in the weld joints so, multi objective optimization has to be adopted.
- 3 This experimental analysis shows that the optimized flux constituents for high impact strength and low weld HAZ contains 5% calcium fluoride, 8% ferro manganese, and 5% nickel oxide.

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